

Synthesis and Studies on some Biheterocyclic Compounds

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In continuation of our work on heterocyclic nitrogen compounds, we report here the synthesis of a series of new fused pyrazoline, isoxazoline, pyrimidine and pyrimidinethione derivatives (2-6) because of their biological¹ and industrial² uses.

Results and Discussion

1,3-Oxazolone-2-methyl-4-arylidine derivatives (1a-c) were prepared by cyclocondensation of aceturic acid with different aromatic aldehydes³. The presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group in 1a-c led to their reaction with hydrazines according to the reported methods⁴. Thus reaction of 1a-c with hydrazine hydrate in dry alcohol in the presence of glacial acetic acid afforded the corresponding *N*-acetylpyrazolino[3,4-*d*]-1,3-oxazolino-5-aryl derivatives (2a-c). However, the reaction 1a-c with phenyl hydrazine gave *N*-phenylpyrazolino analogs (3a-c) under the influence of piperidine catalyst. Also, the activation exerted by the carbonyl group on the exocyclic double bond in 1a-c renders them available for the addition of various amino compounds, e.g. hydroxylamine hydrochloride, urea and thiourea. Thus, interaction of 1a-c with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic sodium hydroxide gave the corresponding 5-arylisoxazolino[3,4-*d*]-1,3-oxazoline derivatives (4a-c), whereas with urea and/or thiourea in ethanol containing hydrochloric acid gave the corresponding pyrimidine⁴ (pyrimidenthione) 6-aryl-1,3-oxazolino[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-6-thione derivatives 5a-c and 6a-c respectively.

Structures of compounds (2-6) were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectra.

The biological screening of some selected biheterocyclic nitrogen compounds (2a, 3a-c, 4a and 5a) was performed against bacterial and fungal spe-

cies *Bacillus P. astidiosus* 86 4, *Bacillus stearothermophilus* 92 L, *Bacillus brevis* 101 and *Aspergillus SP*, *Penicillium SP* and *Alternaria SP*. The structure-activity relationship is obvious as *N*-acetylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]oxazole showed biological activity and potency against bacterial species used and biological inactivity against fungal species. Substituting *N*-acetylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]oxazole with *N*-phenyl analogs increased the biological activities of bacterial species (6-14 mm) but still remaining biological inactive against fungal species.

It is of interest, that the electron-donating substitution in aryl moiety attached with *p*-OCH₃ to such *N*-phenylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]oxazole increased the potency (71 mm) more than the unsubstituted analogs (3a), while substituting with electron-withdrawing groups (such as in 3c) increased the potency more than both unsubstituted and electron-donating substituted analogs (3a, b).

Also, it is obvious that substitution of either *N*-acetyl(phenyl)pyrazole with isoxazole having the same substituent in aryl moiety increased the biological activity, while the substitution with pyrimidine-thione having the same substituent in aryl moiety decreased the potency.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 127B spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO) on a EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

N-Acetylpyrazoline[3,4-*d*]-1,3-oxazolino-5-aryl derivatives (2a-c) : A mixture of 1a-c (0.01 mol) and

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Scheme 1

hydrazine hydrate (0.2 ml, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) containing acetic acid (1 ml) was refluxed for 10–15 h, then the reaction mixture was filtered while hot, concentrated to one-third of its original volume, poured in ice-water with vigorous stirring and left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from proper solvent (yields 20–33%): **2a**, m.p. 210° (MeOH), $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300–3 450 (NH), 1 520–1 575 (C=N), 700 cm^{-1} (Ar-substituted), δ 1.3 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 5.0–5.5 (2H, m, isoxazolone and pyrazolone protons), 7.5–8.0 (5H, m, ArH); **b**, 120° (EtOH); **c**, 122° (EtOH).

N-Phenylpyrazolino[3,4-d]-1,3-oxazolono-5-aryl derivatives (**3a-c**): A mixture of **1a-c** (0.01 mol) and phenylhydrazine (0.2 ml, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) and refluxed for 10–15 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered while hot, concentrated to one-third of its original volume, poured in ice-water mixture with stirring for 10 min and left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solids were washed with water, dried and crystallised (yields 15–21%): **3a**, m.p. 200° (MeOH); **b**, 100° (EtOH); **c**, 90° (MeOH); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 520–1 575 (C=N), 700 cm^{-1} (Ar-substituted), δ 1.4 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 5.0–5.5 (2H, m, isoxazolone and pyrazolone

protons), 6.8–7.5 (5H, m, ArH).

Isoxazolino[3,4-d]-1,3-oxazolono-5-aryl derivatives (4a-c): A mixture of **1a-c** (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) containing 2% sodium hydroxide (1 ml) was refluxed for 10–15 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered while hot, the filtrate concentrated to one-third of its original volume, poured in ice-water mixture with stirring for 15 min and left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solids were washed with water, dried and crystallised (yields 15–19%): **4a**, m.p. 175° (MeOH); **b**, 155° (EtOH); **c**, 160° (MeOH); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 540–1 575 (C=N), 700 cm^{-1} (Ar-substituted), δ 1.5 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 2.3–2.6 (2H, m, isoxazolone protons), 7.0–7.5 (5H, m, ArH).

6-Aryl-1,3-oxazolino[4,5-d]pyrimidine-6-thione derivatives (5a-c, 6a-c): A mixture of an ethanolic solution of **1a-c** (0.01 mol) and urea or thiourea (4 g) and concentrated HCl (20 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then filtered while hot, allowed to cool and neutralised with 5 N NaOH. The resulting solids were washed with water, dried and crystallised (yields **5**, 18–21%; **6**, 27–30%): **5a**, m.p. 290° (MeOH); **b**, 110° (MeOH); **c**, 310° (EtOH); **6a**, 205° (EtOH); **b**, 210° (MeOH); **c**, 150° (EtOH); **6** $\nu_{\max}$ 3 360–3 450 (NH), 1 450 (C=N), 1 350 (C=S), 700 cm^{-1} (Ar-substituted), δ 1.5–1.6 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 5.8–6.3 (1H, m, isoxazolone proton), 6.8–7.5 (6H, m, ArH).

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